

Employability and Job Satisfaction of the School of Education Graduates: An Online Tracer Report

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ABSTRACT

Tracing the graduates of the School of Education (SED) indisputably provides a relevant data on their employability and their job satisfaction. The online tracer report chronicled sixty alumni who responded to the questionnaire floated on the Google Form platform. The year the alumni graduated from San Isidro College covered from 1985 to 2020. Their response as to the time duration they were able to get employment indicated 43% in a matter of months and 36% within 1 to 2 years. As to their job satisfaction 48% rated that they were *very satisfied* and 47% were *satisfied* with their jobs affirming that their Alma Mater had honed them to be prepared in their teaching craft.

Subject Area

Tracer Study

Keywords: *Tracer Study, Employability, Job Satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

After graduation, the School of Education (SED) graduates of San Isidro College start their journey towards scouting for jobs to find their niches in the community they lived in. This phenomenon is true to almost all graduates, considering that this young and budding men and women are desirous to get a job and become one of the earners in society. However, since the BEEd and the BSEd are PRC board courses, the graduates generally have to stay awhile for their review classes and prepare for the Licensure Examinations for Professional Teachers (LEPT). This is one reason why a number of Education graduates would take a year or two to be able to get employment because they still have to review for the exam then wait for the results.

There are some alumni who after graduation opt to get a job immediately to earn money. Some apply for a job not necessarily as teachers but in some other jobs that will accept them for the meantime that they are still waiting for their LEPT results. There are also private schools that will immediately hire fresh graduates, providing them the opportunity to immediately land a job. For the San Isidro College graduates, many Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS)

would prefer to hire them. It is at this juncture that the SED wanted to trace its graduates as to their employability and their whereabouts after they leave the portals of their Alma Mater.

A tracer study is one important tool that could be a source of information as to what happened to the graduates of academic programs in higher education institutions (Gines, 2004). A tracer study tracks the whereabouts of the graduates to check on how institutions document the demographic profile and evaluate the quality of graduates in the different work stations. It is one gauge on the effectiveness of the programs offered by the institution and on checking the quality of graduates produced by the institution. This evaluation of the school could provide a basis for further improvement of the curriculum and its implementation.

The School of Education had been in existence in 1969 (BSEd) and 1995 (BEEd) and it has not published a report on the whereabouts of its graduates. Considering that this is a very important support document for accreditation of its programs, the PAASCU consultant advised the SED administration to conduct a tracer study of its graduates. Tadlas (2021) conducted a tracer study of the SED graduates from academic year 2016-2017 up to 2018-2019. Her findings showed that most of the graduates who responded were females belonging to the 20-22 years old age bracket, single, residents of the city, graduated in the academic year 2017-2018, and major in English. Their first job was in the academe, stayed for one year to less than 2 years, is on contractual status, and working locally. They have a teaching position, receiving a monthly salary of ₱ 5,000.00 to less than ₱ 10,000.00 and were connected in the private sector.

The present study is conducted virtually with the survey questionnaire given to the SED alumni/graduates via Google form. The purpose is to trace the SED graduates as to their demographic profile and their employability and job satisfaction.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The study is anchored on the premise that quality assurance could be measured by the quality of graduates an institution of higher learning can produce. These could be traced according to the employability of the graduates and their job satisfaction. A tracer study could serve as the tool through which the graduates could be tracked as to what happened to them, where they are employed, and how they fare in their jobs. Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

Students go to school with the purpose of attaining education that will prepare them for work in the future. This is the functionalist theory of education where knowledge, skills attitudes and socialization are essential. Education provides the students the needed knowledge and skills that they will need to apply in their future jobs according to their qualifications. Melvin Tumin (cited

by Bryant, 2013) explained that the theory shows the role on how education and school played their roles to produce competent individuals that will help the job market develop. Education provides the avenue to demonstrate the relevance of achievement, competition and equal opportunity in the workplace.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study traced the whereabouts of the School of Education (SED) graduates of San Isidro College after they leave the portals of their Alma mater. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the SED graduates as tracked online in terms of :
 - 1.1 Year graduated from San Isidro College;
 - 1.2 civil service eligibility;
 - 1.3 year licensed (LEPT) earned;
 - 1.4 agency they are connected;
 - 1.5 ranks in their jobs; and
 - 1.6 salary range?
2. What is the employability wait-time period of the graduates to get a job?
3. How satisfied are the graduates with their present jobs?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the descriptive method of research. Due to the restrictions on the face-to-face conduct of the survey during this time of the pandemic, the survey questionnaire was floated online via the Google form. A delimitation of this kind of survey is that the respondents are only those who answered the survey questionnaire online and the researchers could not compel all the graduates/alumni to respond to the survey.

Since the participants are dependent upon those who willingly submitted their responses via the Google form, there were only 60 participants in a matter of one month's exposure to the questionnaire. These 60 participants are San Isidro's College graduates from the BSEd and BEEd curriculum where 41 are now working in the public sector, 10 in the private agency, 4 are OFWs and 5 are in other jobs. The gathered data were treated using the frequency and percentage.

San Isidro College is a private sectarian school established more than 70 years in July 1949 by the Jesuits and was turned over to the American Sisters of the Congregation of Saint Joseph of Newark. Sister Mary Redemptra McConnel, CSJ, began the 18 years' journey of administering the school starting in 1953. The School of Education opened in 1969 for the BSEd program and in 1995 for the BEEd program. In 1971, the Sisters of Saint Joseph of Newark were called back to the United States of America, hence turning over the school to the Prelature of Malaybalay headed by Bishop Francisco Claver, S.J. DD, who invited the Marist Brothers to manage the school up to 14 years.

In the mid 80's (1985), San Isidro College saw change in the administration. The Missionary of the Benedictine Sisters took over the administration and management of the school with the Bishop of Bukidnon, Bishop Gaudencio Rosales, DD as the chairperson of the Board of Trustees. During the School Year 1991-1992 the Bachelor of Science in Elementary Education was implemented and was granted approval in 1995 with a GR No. 029, s. 1995. The Bachelor of

Science in Secondary Education was implemented and granted approval in 1969 with the GR No. 189, s. 1969, offering the following majors: Religious Education, Mathematics, English and Filipino. Religious Education was later changed to Values Education in 2017-2018.

From school year 2000 -2002, Bishop Pacana appointed Sis. Lilia U. Nuesca, FdCC, (June 2001) as the school President; and Sis. Nally G. Espiritu, of the Missionary Congregation of Mary (MCM) as Finance Office. Sr. Nuesca was followed by Sr. Luzviminda G. Mojica, FdCC. In 2006, Reverend Fr. Virgilio H. Delfin, CPA, DBM started as the President of San Isidro College up to the present.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic profile of the SED graduates

Table 1 illustrates the year the SED alumni graduated from San Isidro College. As shown in the Table most of those who responded (65%) were from those who graduated during the academic year 2011-2020. This could account for the fact that there were also a good number of graduates during these years. It also indicates that many of the graduates during this period are more adept to the new technology and thereby they can easily respond to the survey questionnaire virtually. Since these are mostly teachers, they practically know how to manipulate their computers and could easily get updates from their Alma Mater. Responding to the call for a tracer study would not be difficult for them if they know the technology.

Table 1. SED alumni graduates categorized according to the year they graduated

Year SED Alumni Graduated	<i>f</i>	%
1985-1989	3	5
1990-2000	6	10
2001-2010	12	20
2011-2020	39	65
Total	60	100

Table 2 shows the civil service eligibility of the SED alumni graduates. It is noted that there were SED graduates who took the civil service career examination with the hope of being able to work in the government or private agency as permanent workers. While it is true that as teachers they have to take the PRC Board examination to obtain the Licensure Examination for Professional Teachers, which the results are usually announced by the Professional Regulation Commission every March and September. It is noted that out of the 60 respondents only 5 took the Civil Service Career Examination and the great majority (55) did not take this examination. This could be attributed to the fact that as teacher graduates; they are more inclined to take the LEPT rather than the CSC examinations.

Table 2. Civil Service eligibility of the SED alumni graduates

Civil Service Eligibility taken	<i>f</i>	%
Professional career Civil Service Examination	4	6.7
Non-Professional Career CS Examination	1	1.7
None	55	91.7
Total	60	100

Table 3 displays the year when the respondents passed the Licensure for Professional Teacher Examination. The Licensure Examination for Professional Teachers (LEPT) indicated that from

2011 to 2020, forty out of the 60 respondents passed the exam. There were 5 respondents however who did not respond to this question.

Table 3. Distribution of respondents who passed the Licensure Examination for Professional Teachers (LEPT)

Year the SED graduate obtained the Licensure Examination for Professional Teachers (LEPT)	<i>f</i>	%
1991-1999	8	13.33
2000-2010	7	11.67
2011-2015	20	33.33
2016-2020	20	33.33
No response	5	8.33
Total	60	100

It is good to note that the result of the LEPT during the Academic year 2016-2017 up to 2019-2020 as shown in Table 4 indicated that San Isidro’s passing percentage rate were above the national passing rates in March 2017, March 2018, and March 2019 for the BSEd. While for the BEEd, the graduates have a higher passing percentage rate on March 2017, March 2018, March 2019 and September 2019. These results in many ways justified the responses of the participants in the study that a good number of them passed the LEPT during the years 2011 to 2020. Passing the Licensure Examination opens the doors for the graduates to get employment in the public schools where the salaries are higher and there is security of tenure.

Table 4. San Isidro’s School of Education LEPT results for the last 5 years

Program	Date of Board Examination	School's Passing Rate	National Passing Rate
Secondary Education (BSEd)	March 2016	33.33	
	March 2017	26.92*	25.46
	September 2017	43.59	46.37
	March 2018	38.10*	29.91
	September 2018	34.88	48.03
	March 2019	44.64*	25.95
	September 2019	31.58	39.69
Elementary Education (BEEd)	March 2016	10.00	
	March 2017	18.75*	10.39
	September 2017	15.79	26.33
	March 2018	54.55*	23.62
	September 2018	14.29	20.29
	March 2019	56.25*	27.29
	September 2019	45.45*	31.34

*Above the National Passing Rate

Table 5 displays the agency or sectors where the SED graduates, in this tracer study are employed. It is observed that the SED graduates find their employment in the public sector where 68.33% of them are immediately absorbed in the jobs. Most of them are in the Department of Education and in the National High School. When the graduates passed the LEPT they generally apply in the DepEd both in the elementary (BEEd) and secondary (BSEd) levels, where they are also assigned in schools with vacancies especially in distant areas. After some years, they can apply for transfer of school locations and the new teachers are again assigned in the far areas. They

are lucky if their assignment is in the city proper or in nearby barangays. Some teacher applicants who could not bear their assignment in the far flung areas opt to stay in the private schools within the city or within areas accessible to transportation. They usually apply in the BUACS schools and very likely they find themselves at ease or confident in the private schools owing to the fact that they also graduated in a private school. Maybe, they find no difficulty in adjusting to the kind of valuing system in BUACS schools as these too, are Catholic schools like San Isidro College.

Table 5. Agencies/Sectors where the SED graduates are employed.

Employment Agency/Sector	<i>f</i>	%
Public sector/agency	41	68.33
Private sector/agency	10	16.67
OFW	4	6.67
Others	5	8.33
Total	60	100

Table 6 shows the rank or position that the SED graduates have in their jobs. Generally, the greater bulk of their employment is in teaching. This is what they were trained for-- to be a teacher. Some became administrators and work in the administrative positions. There were those who are detained in offices, while a few have other jobs, aside from teaching, administration, and office personnel. The respondents showed that the training they received in the undergraduate program was very much related to the tasks they perform in their current employment.

Table 6. Rank or position the SED graduates have in their jobs.

Employment Agency/Sector	<i>f</i>	%
Teacher	46	76.67
Administrative	6	10
Office	3	5
Others	5	8.33
Total	60	100

Table 7 illustrates the salary range that the employed SED alumni have in their present jobs. As shown in the Table a good number of these graduates claimed to have salaries within the range of ₱21,000 -30,999 monthly bracket. This is expected because they worked in the DepEd and they have a standardized salary grade. Those handling administrative positions have higher salary grade and there were 4 of them with salary range above ₱30,999 bracket. There was even one with a salary grade within ₱41,000-50,999 and there is one with a salary grade above 51,000. These findings indicate that a good number of the SED graduates are enjoying their salary range. Those employed in the private sectors have lower salary range, considering that the agency also has limited budget for their employees.

Table 7. Salary Range the SED graduates have in their jobs.

Salary Range (₱)	f	%
Below 15,000	8	13.33
15,001 – 20,999	5	8.33
21,000 – 30,999	43	71.77
31,000 – 40,999	2	3.33
41,000 – 50,999	1	1.77
Above 51,000	1	1.77
Others	5	8.33
Total	60	100

Employability of the SED Graduates

Table 8 illustrates the wait-time that the SED graduates waited before they acquired their present jobs. It is revealed from the Table that a good number (43.11%) got the present jobs just in a span of few months after their graduation. This could mean that the graduates can easily get employment. There were 38.33% who got their present jobs after waiting for one to two years. This could be because after graduation, the graduates still have to do their review for the Licensure Exam. After they took their Exam, they still have to wait for the results. If they passed the LEPT, then they will apply for a job at the DepEd and will have to wait for their assignments, although they surely will be absorbed in the DepEd or the National High Schools, because of their eligibility.

While most of the graduates were able to get immediate employment, especially for the LEPT passers, there were also those who took some 3 to 5 years or even beyond 5 years to land a job. There could be some reasons related to health, family, marriage, childbirth, sickness, problems, and other reasons.

Table 8. The wait-time gap of the employability of the SED graduates in their present job

Duration	f	%
Months	25	43.11
1 – 2 Years	23	38.33
3- 5 Years	6	10.33
5 year or more	6	10.33
Total	60	100

When asked as to whether they have other employment before their present jobs, 39 or 65% of the respondents replied affirmatively, while 21 or 35% replied negatively. Matrix 1 shows the jobs the graduates have during their first employment, prior to their present jobs.

Matrix 1. Jobs of the SED graduates during their first employment and its agencies

Jobs taken by the SED graduates prior to their present employment	What the job is or where the job is
Administrative Assistant at Emphasis Law Office	Catholic Schools
FULL TIME HIGH SCHOOL TEACHER AND PART TIME COLLEGE INSTRUCTOR, FULL TIME PUBLIC CATECHIST	Secondary Teacher at San Andres High School-Maramag, Call Center Agent at Cyber City Telecommunication Services-Davao City
Private school teacher	Daycare Worker
Loyola High School, Don Carlos, Bukidnon	Elementary & Kindergarten Teacher at SIC
ASIAN HYBRID SEEDS TECH INC	customer service
Booking I at Monde Nissin	HR Staff

Local Government Unit Bukidnon	Malaybalay City,	Jesuit Retreat House and San Augustin Institute of Technology
TEACHER		Xavier De Damulog School
Teacher		Fr. Leoni Memorial School
JHS Teacher at San Isidro College		Teacher in Private School (Philippines)
Private school Teacher		Kadingilan San Isidro High school
Bukidnon Institute of Catechetics/St. Joseph School, Talakag, Bukidnon	High School,	ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM DEPED MALAYBALAY CITY
BIC /St. Joseph High School, Talakag, Bukidnon		Teacher at Stella Matutina Academy
Tutorial		Liceo de Cagayan University faculty
Pilar High School & La Salle Academy Iligan		Unisilver -sales clerk
Loyola High School - 2016-2018; San Isidro College IBED- 2018-2021	San Isidro	Bukidnon Institute of Catechitics-secretary, Parish Secretary
Bukidnon State University		Bukidnon State University
Private School Teacher		Divine Mercy School of Bukidnon
Private School Teacher		Volunteer Teacher
Kindergarten teacher, Lil Jewels Learning Center		Kinder teacher

Job Satisfaction of the SED Graduates

The SED graduates were asked as to whether they were satisfied with their present job. Contentment in the job allows the person to find satisfaction and happiness in the work they do. Table 9 shows the ratings that the SED graduates gave in their present jobs. It is revealed that the SED graduates were *very satisfied* (48.3%) and *satisfied* (46.7%) with their present job. Only 3 out of the 60 respondents were *moderately satisfied* and nobody was *not satisfied* with his/her job. These findings indicate that generally the SED graduates were contented with their present jobs. The findings support the fact that their training at San Isidro College had prepared them to be knowledgeable in their field. Being skilled and knowledgeable in one's job could increase their motivation to do their job the best they could.

Table 9. Satisfaction ratings of the SED graduates in their present jobs

Satisfaction Ratings	<i>f</i>	%
Very Satisfied	29	48.3
Satisfied	28	46.7
Moderately Satisfied	3	5.0
Not Satisfied	0	0
Total	60	100

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Monitoring and evaluating the SED curriculum and programs could help determine the effectiveness of the training that the graduates achieved. The tracer study is a rich tool to help SED improve and enhance the performance of its graduates when they move out from their Alma Mater to seek employment in the outside world of work. Conducting a tracer study continue to connect the students with their alma mater and with one another. It assesses the employment of the graduates and how far they have become after their college schooling (Regmi, 2009).

This tracer study was conducted online requesting the SED graduates to answer the survey questionnaire via the Google form. The study hopefully reflects the quality of education and the adequacy of the faculty and the training given to the graduates (Kebedom, 2010). From the result

of the tracer, the SED respondents have the greater bulk of graduates during the years 2011-2020. It is also during these years that most of them passed the licensure examination for teachers. Majority of them were employed as teachers in the public sector predominantly in the Department of Education in both the elementary and secondary levels. Their salary generally clustered in the ₱21,000 - 30,999 bracket, with a handful of them earning more than ₱31,000 and above. Their wait time for attaining their employment in their present position ran a span of few months for most of the graduates followed by those who waited from one to two years since they have to take the review classes, prepare for the licensure examination, and wait for the results of the exam, to make them eligible to teach. There were those who waited for 3 years and above and this is not ideal because the graduates might lose the motivation to become a teacher when they are no longer in sync with the trends in teaching. After passing the LEPT, they were able to land a job and consequently are *very satisfied* and *satisfied* with their work.

In summary, the SED graduates are able to find their niches in the community where they lived. The training the SED graduates received from San Isidro College in their undergraduate program helped them to perform their tasks in their current employment. Their General Education courses helped them relate their subjects in real life situations. The Professional Education courses taught them to manage their classes and to plan their lessons well for a more efficient and effective teaching and learning of their major field of specialization.

However, this tracer study needs to include other aspects to find better strategies on the possibility of shortening the wait time for the graduates to get employed; to pass the licensure examination and maybe get the topnotch place; to be more confident in their job search, applying for jobs according to their training and not just any job available.

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